

Special Relativity from Newtonian Mechanics and Rotational Invariance?

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Special relativity is traditionally presented in terms of a transformation between E, p, x, t variables in one frame and another frame moving at constant speed $-v$ relative to the first. In Newtonian mechanics, however, a particle at rest in a rest frame is considered physically different from one which has been acted on by a force and is moving at constant v . As a result, the idea of comparing variables in different frames did not arise fully in Newtonian mechanics for a long time, even though Galilean invariance was known.

Here we argue that one does not need to consider the invariance of equations of motion in frames moving at constant speeds relative to one another in order to obtain special relativistic equations. We suggest that one only needs the notion of force, inertia m_0 and rotational invariance.

Traditional Approach to Obtaining Special Relativity

Traditionally, special relativity is seen as imposing an equivalence between frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ relative to each other. This leads to the idea of a matrix transformation between variables in one frame (such as E, p, x, t) and another. For example, if one considers a rest mass m_0 at rest at $x=0, t$, then in the moving frame one must have $x'=vt'$. Even if one argues that t does not change, x must. One may create a matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} g(v) & vg(v) \\ vg(v) & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

for the transformation. It is not simply x, t that change, but also that m_0 changes into E, p . Given that $x=vt$ and $p=Et$ ($c=1$), the same transformation ((1)) applies. If these are seen as 4-vectors, then in the E, p case, one needs to create equivalence with m_0 which may be done through

$$-EE + ppcc = -m_0m_0cc \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{One readily finds that } E=m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ and } p=m_0v/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((3))$$

The equivalence of the two frames arises from the notion that the same physical system is viewed by the two frames. In Newtonian mechanics, however, a moving particle would be considered an altered system and so we try to examine, in this note, how special relativity may arise without explicitly considering any frames.

Newtonian Mechanics

In Newtonian mechanics, a particle at rest with m_0 is put into motion by a force acting upon it. This force breaks rotational invariance as it points in a particular direction and the particle moves with a velocity vector, which also breaks rotational invariance, in the same direction.

Thus, one moves from a state described by a rotationally invariant inertia m_0 , to one with broken rotational invariance because F and v point in a particular direction. We first note that a force must act in both space and time. In Newtonian mechanics, one considers space and time to be independent. In particular, a clock is on a wall and one has positions in space which seem to be independent of the clock. The clock or time becomes relevant if one wishes to describe changes in position relative to the clock reading.

Even though a force breaks rotational symmetry, one may create two math objects

$$A1 \text{ (rotationally invariant)} = \text{Integral } F \cdot dr \text{ ((4a)) and}$$

$$A2 \text{ vector (breaks rotational invariance)} = \text{Integral } F dt \text{ ((4b))}$$

The first does not break rotational invariance, while the second does which is interesting because the original m_0 also does not break rotational invariance. One has the further relation:

$$dr/dt = v \text{ (vectors) ((5))}$$

((4a)) and ((4b)) appear in Newtonian mechanics and represent two physically different quantities, namely kinetic energy and momentum. The first is linked with an interaction with a potential over a spatial range, while the second is linked with a quick hit in a very tiny dx . If one considers x, t independent, it is unusual that using both gives rise to two very different, yet physically relevant quantities ((4a)) and ((4b)). We suggest instead that given that ((4a)) and ((4b)) are linked, one should also consider x and t as linked and not independent. In other words, we agree with the statement in (1), that spacetime is not simply a math construct, but has physical relevance.

We next consider the notion that even though F points in a specific direction, one may create scenarios with the same F magnitude pointing in all directions. This would restore rotational invariance. We suggest that one may create two rotationally invariant quantities linked to F , i.e. using $A1$ and $A2$, namely

$$A1 \cdot A1 \text{ and } A2 \cdot A2 \text{ ((6))}$$

From ((4)), one should use $A1 \cdot A1$ and not $A1$.

Even though both terms in ((6)) are rotationally invariant, it is not clear what to do with them. We suggest that given that m_0 (before the force acts) is rotationally invariant, it might be possible to use $A1$ and $A2 \cdot A2$ to create the rotational invariant $m_0 C$, where C is a constant. To do so, we work in one dimension and consider

$$A1 = \text{Integral } dA1 = \text{integral } v \cdot dA2 \text{ ((7))}$$

We then consider a linear equation of the rotationally invariant terms with a minus sign because one wishes to eliminate the effect of the force to obtain a rotational invariant linked to m_0 . We

note that from ((4)), A_1 and A_2 are on the same footing, so if one uses $A_2 \cdot A_2$, then one should use m_0^2 and A_1^2 . This leads to

$$-A_1^2 + B A_2 \cdot A_2 = -m_0^2 C \quad ((8))$$

We assume that A_2 , a vector, is proportional to the v vector. Thus, for $v=0$,

$$A_1 = m_0 \sqrt{C} \quad ((9))$$

Next, we take d/dv of ((8))

$$-A_1 dA_1 + B A_2 dA_2 = 0 \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Using ((4)) } -A_1 + A_2/v = 0 \text{ or } A_1 v = A_2 B \quad ((10))$$

((10)) is of the identical form of $x=vt$, yet A_1 and A_2 have been created by intertwining dt and dx with Force.

((8)) then implies that: $A_1^2 (-1 + Bv^2) = -m_0^2 C$ or

$$A_1 = m_0 \sqrt{C} / \sqrt{1 - Bv^2} \text{ and } A_2 = Bv A_1 \quad ((11))$$

If $B=1/c^2$ and $C=c^2$, then A_1 is E from special relativity and A_2 is momentum. Thus, we suggest that one may obtain special relativistic results directly from Newtonian mechanics, by paying attention to the notion of rotational invariance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, special relativistic equations are traditionally obtained by considering the equivalence of a physical system as seen by two frames moving at a constant speed of $-v$ relative to each other. This leads to the notion of a matrix transformation (Lorentz transformation) between the four vectors (x, ct) and (x', ct') and the separate $(m_0 c, 0)$ and (E, pc) . Ultimately, one has $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = mv / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$.

We suggest that one may obtain these same results using Newtonian mechanics and considerations of rotational invariance. We first note that one starts with a rest mass (inertia) which is rotationally invariant. If a force acts on this, rotational invariance is broken, but one may nevertheless create two math quantities: $A_1 = \int F \cdot dr$ (rotationally invariant) and $A_2 = \int F dt$ (vector) ((12)). (As is known from Newtonian mechanics, both are physically relevant.) We further argue that if one consider all possible directions of F , one has the notion of rotational invariance and may consider the two terms A_1^2 and $A_2 \cdot A_2$. We multiply A_1 by itself because of the relations ((12)). We then go on to argue that one may be able to take these two rotationally invariant quantities and subtract them with a possible weight to obtain the invariant m_0^2 . We show that this leads to the result: $A_1 = m_0 \sqrt{C} / \sqrt{1 - Bv^2}$ where C and B are constants) and $A_2 = Bv A_1$. These are the special relativistic equations if $B = 1/c^2$.

References

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